

Women and the Realities of the Glass Ceiling : Investors' Perspective

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Abstract : *In the present times when issues pertaining to women, their societal and corporate roles and talks inclusion have hogged the limelight, a reality check of the roles and challenges of women is an absolute necessity. The study draws its distinctive character from being a perceptual study of the investors, who put their money into a company and ultimately translate corporate inclusion, if at all, into their investment decisions. The investors' perceptions with regards to women were analysed to conclude that advances were being made in mental and societal inclusion of women, yet a lot still remains unaccomplished. The clichéd roles pertaining to rearing children and family responsibilities still are perceived to be women's restricted area, though women have been recorded to break the societal and self-imposed barriers to take the fight to success and corporate excellence. The glass ceiling still remain though has noticeable cracks in it.*

Keywords : Gender Challenges, Glass Ceiling, Investment Decision, Social Inclusion, Resource Based Theory.

Introduction

Economic growth and development remain the ultimate objective for which every economy aspires and toils. Creation of a balanced society offering equal opportunities for all irrespective of the gender, caste, religion remains a natural consequence of growth and development. In an economy like India which is touted to be next superpower, balance and equality assume all the more importance as skewed flight is neither sustainable nor just. In the pursuit of social and financial inclusiveness, equality of opportunities and decision making is imperative. This equality in participation not only lends credibility and sustainability to the growth model but also creates a healthy prosperous society.

One of the major impediments in this growth spree remains the age-old and clichéd glass ceiling. The fairer sex has always strived hard to garner its share or opportunities in the male dominated society in various walks of life. Unfortunately, this gender biasedness is not only all pervasive but also ubiquitous. Women since times immemorial have had to either stifle their professional aspirations or fall prey to the vicious traps weaved in the society which has also found it hard to accept women at equal footing.

Discrimination and exclusion have been pervasive in varying dimensions, in diverse fields and almost at all levels. Be it in the pretext of caste system, financial well being, haves and have-nots or skin color, administrations have not been able to level the play field completely. Discriminatory practices have known the Indian lands from the times immemorial which have been brought to record in the epic writings as well. Amongst those excluded, women have continued to be victimized by exclusionary practices in almost all fields. Glass ceiling, gender biasness, gender divide or call it by whatever name, women are still struggling to get their due. In the Indian lands with rich heritage and high reverence for women and female power, where females are worshipped as Goddesses, revered as source of life, it is indeed painful to realize the women continue to struggle in the cobwebs created by the male dominated society. Instances of discrimination against women, implicit and explicit impediments in social, religious, political and corporate life continue to keep these ladies to the margins denying them the center stage. This all, in the face of huge strides of progress, glory and global dominance taken by India whereby world acknowledges the clout of the developing economy.

Initiatives have been taken in India to put women at par with men in various fields. Be it quotas in political institutions, panchayati raj institutions, the fight for entry of women in traditional places of worship, merit based long due entry in armed forces and flying of fighter planes, the mandatory quotas on boards of companies as prescribed by the Companies Act, 2013 to name a few.

In Indian context, the indisputable glory and status call for more responsibility to grow and sustain on the strong pillars of equality, inclusion and fairness. With social inclusion being the buzzword in growing times and India hoarding the strong potential to grow, can the avoidable and manageable biases not be avoided? The study is motivated by the growth trajectory of the Indian economy juxtaposed against the evident imbalances especially against women and their potential to restrict the benefits due to a robust economy like India. In the backdrop of growing awareness on indispensability of inclusionary practices

and policies, the study intends to capture the perceptions of investors regarding the role of men and women in Indian society, challenges faced by Indian women and their influence on investment decisions. With an intent to gauge the perceptions of investors with regards to women and their challenges, the study is an attempt to paint a realistic picture of Indian women amidst the tall claims of gender equality: social and financial.

2. Theoretical Basis

The theoretical underpinnings which highlight the role of women in carrying out governance functions provide a basis for study of association between performance and gender diversity. These include the agency theory and resource dependency. Agency theory suggests that a more diverse team of principals may ensure better monitoring of managers (agents), as diversity increases board independence (Randoy, Thomsen and Oxelheim, 2006). The proponents of agency theory intend to reduce agency costs through alignment of interests of managers and shareholders by effective monitoring through an efficient and effective board. Gender diversity on the corporate boards can help enhance effectiveness which in turn can lead to good performance, as a result of wider perspectives and more exhaustive decision-making process. The positive influence of diversity as a result of more effective monitoring function has been analysed in prior research studies in different contexts: measuring the impact through various accounting measures (Krishnan and Park, 2005, Jurkus, Park and Woodard, 2007), through audit function (Carter et al, 2007) and the similar kinds.

The resource dependence theory views women (diversity) as one of the important instruments in the hands of management to access the various resources critical to firm's success available in the external environment (Johnson, Daily and Ellstrand, 1996). More diverse board will help draw the essential strategic fit with the dynamic and complex business culture. A gender diverse board could benefit from a greater understanding of its customers (Carter, Simkins and Simpson, 2003) and from a wider and in depth knowledge of the industry or choice of access to finance, also will help tap more information sources though sometimes at the expense of less decisiveness (Randoy, Thomsen and Oxelheim, 2006).

There is an additional view to support the gender diversity on corporate boards i.e. the resource based view. It propagates that corporate performance is strongly influenced by physical, organizational and human resources that are available to management (Barney, 1991) and undoubtedly these must be valuable, rare, have imperfect imitability and no strategically equivalent substitutes. Gender

diversity and balance between both genders can become a source of competitive advantage (Watson, Kumar and Michaelson, 1993; Farewell and Hersch, 2001), provided that each gender contributes to management in a different and complementary way.

Corporate sector contributes profusely to the economic development of the country and in building up a healthy and equitable society. The businesses do not operate in vacuum rather share a relationship of interdependency and mutual exchange with the society. They strongly affect and are affected by developments, notions and ideas of the society. Through business activities and initiatives, the larger objective of a socially inclusive and healthy society can be hastened and smoothened.

Inclusion: societal and corporate, has been acknowledged as the stepping stone to sustainable growth and development world over. Countries in their pursuit of excelling and growing in the competitive times have been trying all tricks in the book to achieve that competitive edge and also sustain it to qualify as world leaders. Exclusionary practices where on one side are regarded as discriminatory, also throw a spanner in the wheels of economic and social development. When talks of equality are abound, are revered as indispensable and supported by evidence to lead to numero uno position, global economies are getting prepared to adopt inclusion till the last mile. With international agencies like World Bank, OECD, UNESCO and UN explicitly chartering the roads to inclusivity and embarking on a regime of making all a part of growth journey at micro and macro levels, nations do not have much to choose from in terms of policies. Hence, the case for comprehending the role of women and their challenges becomes pertinent.

3. Methodology

The primary objective of the study is to comprehend the perceptions of the common investor with respect to the women and their roles and challenges in Indian context. To gauge the perception of investors, data has been collected in a span of about five months (November, 2022 to March 2023) from a well-balanced sample in terms of gender, age, income and investment experience of the respondent.

The population for the study was the investing community across India spanning across different demographic categories. Adopting purposive and judgement

sampling, responses to questionnaire-based survey have been gathered from 400 respondents. Of these 60 questionnaires were found to be unfit for analysis on account of incomplete questions (29), multiple options where one was needed (23) and bias of neutrality (8). The final analysis has been done with respect to 340 respondents where responses were complete in all respects.

For analysis of the data appropriate statistical techniques have been used to justify the objective of the study and draw meaningful conclusions from the analysis. Calculation of simple frequencies and percentages, rankings and chi-square test for association have been used for different aspects of the survey. The Chi-Squared Test of Association allows the comparison of two attributes (i.e. qualitative variables) in a sample of data to determine if there is any relationship between them. The idea behind this test is to compare the observed frequencies with the frequencies that would be expected if the null hypothesis of no association / statistical independence were true.

3.1. Sample Profile

An attempt was made to include diverse investors in the survey: diversity on account of gender, educational qualification, monthly income and experience in investing. These were identified as important attributes of the investor profile which can impact their perceptions and considerations while making investment and their beliefs about role and contribution of women towards society in general and corporate boards specifically.

a) Qualification : Across gender, the sample for study was distributed as 192 males (56.5%) and 148 females (46.5%) who also were diverse with respect to qualifications and monthly income. In the sample, post graduates constituted the highest percentage accounting for 42.1% (143) of the total sample followed by graduates who were 73 of the totals of 340. Amongst the undergraduate respondents (17), females were larger in number as is case for the highest qualification of doctorate. Females, as revealed by the sample, did not lag behind on account of qualifications and this, hence, does not hold ground as a reason for denial of equal opportunities to them. Doctorate females accounted for almost 20% of the female sample size while this percentage was mere 11% for males. Post graduate female investors were 40% of all females and the proportion of professional investors was a good 15% affirming stance of no dearth of qualified females.

Table-1 : Qualifications of Respondents Across Gender

HIGHEST QUALIFICATION	GENDER		
	Male	Female	Total
Under graduate	5	12	17
Graduate	46	27	73
Post Graduate	85	58	143
Professional	34	22	56
Doctorate	22	29	51
Total	192	148	340

This association of gender with qualification of the respondents was also checked with the help of chi-square statistic ($\chi^2= 10.9$; p value 0.027) which was found to be significant at 5% level of significance establishing that highest qualification of investor was statistically significantly different across gender.

b) Monthly income : Income, undoubtedly, is an important determinant and influencer of investment decision by investors. An effort was made to gauge the monthly income of the respondent across five income categories to correlate it with basis of decision making of the investors. Distribution of respondents across different income categories was balanced in the sample with 25% of investors earning more than Rs. 1,00,000 per month, 27% in the category of 50,000-1,00,000, 23% earning less than 25,000 and 24% in the income bracket of 25,000-50,000. These income classifications however, were found to differ across gender groups wherein clearly women were found to lie in the lower income brackets.

Women in the higher income bracket (more than Rs. 75,000 per month) constituted mere 21% of the total female sample which stood in stark contrast to 44% of all males in this high-income group. On the outset, this seems to be loosely pointing towards the widely talked about ubiquitous pay-gaps and denial of equal financial and professional status to women.

The differences across male and female respondents with respect to monthly income were also found to be statistically significant when examined through chi-square test ($\chi^2= 23.0$; p value <0.001). Sample statistics confirm the differences across gender groups with respect to income earned by them establishing that there lies a significant difference in monthly income across gender.

Table-2 : Monthly Income of Respondents Across Gender

Monthly income	GENDER		
	Male	Female	Total
Less than Rs. 25,000	35	42	77
Rs 25,000 to Rs. 50,000	39	43	82
Rs. 50,000 to Rs. 75000	31	32	63
Rs. 75,000 to Rs. 1,00,000	22	11	33
More than Rs. 1,00,000	65	20	85
Total	192	148	340

c) Investment experience : Investors' experience in terms of number of years they have been investing in corporate securities was examined to understand their perspective vis-à-vis their investment decisions and considerations involved therein.

A large percentage of the sample (68% approx.) was new investors with experience in the corporate investment less than 5 years. Government driven policy initiatives to make capital markets an attractive investment option for the investing community have resulted in attracting investors' money and attention towards these investment options. Female investors were in low numbers in higher experience categories highlighting the hitherto restrictive and conservative approach of females while making investments in corporate securities. These differences, however, were found to be significant at only 10% level of significance ($\chi^2= 8.24$; p value 0.083) which establishes the association across gender and investment experience as loosely significant.

Table-3 : Investment Experience of Respondents Across Gender

How long you have been investing in corporate securities?	GENDER		
	Male	Female	Total
Less than a year	60	65	125
1-5 years	66	44	110
5-10 years	26	21	47
10- 15 years	19	7	26
More than 15 years	21	11	32
Total	192	148	340

4. Results and Findings

4.1. Perceived Roles of Men and Women in Society

Role of men and women in society seem to be divided more so in Indian society. These role differences emerge more from Indian mindsets, where women and their prime responsibilities were acknowledged to be centered around household, kitchen and child rearing jobs. The professional responsibilities and those relating to management of funds remain undoubtedly a man's area. If it related to kitchen and household chores or nurturing children or any of their needs, women were expected to assume it as their prime duty and undiluted priority. However, with changing times and mindset, tall claims of women empowerment and efforts towards breaking the glass ceiling, it is expected that societal expectations with respect to role of men and women in different walks of life would also change.

Investors' responses with regard to their thinking relating to which of the specified roles could be performed better by men or women or both were recorded. Nine different roles were identified which were attempted to cover prime areas in routine life. The responses were classified according to gender of investor to understand the male and female orientations with respect to different roles and their perceptions regarding ability of men and women to perform them. For further statistical emphasis, chi-square test of association was performed to determine if there is any association between the responses of males and females with respect to each of the identified roles.

Kitchen and household jobs, as the clichéd mind set goes, were found to be still regarded as the prime responsibility of females and surprisingly amongst both genders of investors – males as well as females. These responsibilities were perceived to lie far beyond the work area of males as confirmed by the low frequencies (3.6% for males and 2.7% for females). With more and more women stepping out of their homes for career driven aspirations, need of sharing such responsibilities is becoming inevitable. It was found that with respect to domestic chores, response to the option "both" (as to who can perform the role better) was respectable (29% for males and 33% for females) indicating the inevitability of participation of men given the professional commitments of today's women.

Table-4 : Frequencies (and Percentages) According to Gender for Role of Men and Women and Chi square (p-values) Values

ROLE	MALE			FEMALE			TOTAL			Chi value (p-value)
	Men	Women	Both	Men	Women	Both	Men	Women	Both	
Kitchen and household jobs	7 (3.6)	129 (67.2)	56 (29.2)	4 (2.7)	95 (64.2)	49 (33.1)	11 (3.3)	224 (65.8)	105 (30.9)	0.76 (0.68)
Taking care of children	5 (2.5)	118 (61.6)	69 (35.9)	5 (3.4)	87 (58.8)	56 (37.8)	10 (2.9)	205 (60.3)	125 (36.8)	0.35 (0.84)
Management of funds	72 (37.5)	32 (16.7)	88 (45.8)	34 (23)	31 (20.9)	83 (56.1)	106 (31.2)	63 (18.5)	171 (50.3)	8.23 (0.02)
Business decision making	89 (46.4)	11 (5.7)	92 (47.9)	39 (26.4)	16 (10.8)	93 (62.8)	128 (37.6)	27 (7.9)	185 (54.4)	15.02 (0.00)
Maintaining social relations and interactions	13 (6.8)	66 (34.4)	113 (58.8)	11 (7.4)	51 (34.5)	86 (58.1)	24 (7.1)	117 (34.4)	199 (58.5)	0.06 (0.97)
Leading work teams	57 (29.7)	24 (12.5)	111 (57.8)	31 (20.9)	31 (20.9)	86 (58.2)	88 (25.9)	55 (16.2)	197 (57.9)	6.15 (0.04)
Social work	33 (17.2)	50 (26.0)	109 (56.8)	15 (10.1)	51 (34.5)	82 (55.4)	48 (14.1)	101 (29.7)	191 (56.2)	4.97 (0.08)
Political activities	100 (52.1)	11 (5.7)	81 (42.2)	77 (52)	9 (6.1)	62 (41.9)	177 (52.1)	20 (5.9)	143 (42)	0.02 (0.99)
Stress management	38 (19.8)	63 (32.8)	91 (47.4)	26 (17.6)	60 (40.5)	62 (41.9)	64 (18.8)	123 (36.2)	153 (45)	2.162 (0.34)

Note: Figures in parenthesis in columns of male, female and both indicate gender wise percentages and in chi-square column indicate the p-values to highlight statistical significance

The association of male and female perceptions gender for kitchen and household jobs lack statistical significance indicating no significant association with respect to these roles (chi-square value of 0.76). Kitchen jobs still are regarded as the primary duty of women in Indian society even in today’s transformed times. Another primary role of women lies with respect to motherhood and associated responsibilities of raising children and meeting their different needs. The results again highlighted that it is etched in all mindsets that children should remain a priority of women and what men do as fathers is far above essential. Built upon the Indian value system and image of ideal women, this role is perceived unanimously as better performed by women appearing more like their core competence. Women seem to acknowledge their prime responsibilities as domestic work driven by their upbringing in a patriarchal culture. Maintaining social relations and interactions exhibit similarity of opinion of males and females

as well. No significant differences across gender have been observed for the role pertaining to social interactions where in higher frequency lies for “both” (58%) indicating that this has not been recognized as a domain area for either males or females and both can do it successfully. On probing further, higher percentage of responses were noted for females (34% approximately) leading to conclude that females vis-à-vis males are better at social relations and interactions.

Consistency in responses of male and female respondents was also noted for political activities which are acknowledged as the forte of men. Investors were found to be of the opinion that men have the finer sensibilities to handle and contribute to political activities (52%). Though males were acknowledged to be deft in handling political affairs yet the option that both men and women can handle political matters also garnered support of more than 40% of investors. Homogeneity in responses of males and females is confirmed by the insignificance of results of chi-squared test of association. Similarly, no association was observed for the role pertaining to stress management where the options of women and both men and women have responses of 40% of respondents each. Stress management is perceived more as a situational trait emanating from experiences and preferences rather than from gender based biological characteristics. Males and females seemed to have similar stance, which failed the test of statistical association and hence responses of males and females with respect to better stress management were homogeneous (associated).

Relationships through chi-square test of association were recorded for roles relating to management of funds and business decision making. 37.5% of male respondents believed that men could manage funds better while only 23% of females acknowledged men as better fund managers. Females according to 16.7% of males could effectively manage funds but larger numbers of females (21%) regarded their fairer sex as better managers of funds and finances. 45% of males and 56% of females believe that sound financial management can be ensured by both. Results clarified that males did hold reservations with respect to female ability to manage financial issues while women reposed faith in financial abilities of females. These differences in mindset, indicative of male dominance especially in financial and critical matters was confirmed of its statistical significance through the values for chi-square test.

Very similar results were noted for the role of business decision making where again men seemed to believe that critical business decisions could be better arrived at and implemented by males (46%). Women, on the other hand,

underrated men on this and casted their vote for “both” (almost 63%) defying the male notion that women are less capable to make business decisions. Women seemed to no longer support the age-old belief of restricted capabilities of women rather believe that empowered women of today are capable to compete with men and make sustainable decisions relating to business issues. Responses culled from the survey emphasized that women differed significantly from men in context of the role relating to leading work teams and social work as well. For these roles also, men regarded people of their gender (males) as better suited than females while females held different opinion as lower percentage of them believed that men are better suited for the role (20% for leading work teams and 10% for social work). “Both” as a response option was chosen by larger number of females in comparison to males emphasizing that women of today, do not just believe in women power but also have faith in their abilities to perform better in areas which were hitherto regarded as male dominated domains.

Various roles in the society pertaining to household, children, fund management, business decision making, political activities, social welfare etc were put together and responses of sampled investors were sought. When compared on the basis of gender, it was found that men and women respondents did differ with respect to the suitability of the two for these roles. Males and females were found to hold similar opinions on roles like kitchen and household and taking care of children. With respect to roles relating to business decision making, leading work teams and social work significant associations, statistically confirmed through application of chi-square test of association, were recorded. These indicated the changing mindsets especially of women, who seemed to be defying and denying the traditional restrictions on roles which women can assume in society. Women investors and their responses advocated their ability and intention to participate equally with men in all jobs unshackling the traditional mindsets. It seemed that with changing times, women were moving beyond the clichéd role and starting to take on all responsibilities head on with a winning attitude.

4.2. Perceived Challenges of Inequality Combated by Indian Women

For this, first the respondents were asked about the ubiquitous challenges which women in India are known to be facing. It meant to understand the extent and spread of these challenges in different walks of life like legal rights, occupational choices, property rights, pay gap, opportunities for leadership positions, board directorships and the like. Respondents were asked about these different areas and their feelings regarding the extent of inequality prevalent in society which

posed challenges for women. This was expected to provide input for better insights into the real position of women and gravity of situation vis-à-vis age-old challenges which seem to hinder their growth and empowerment.

Respondents were required to express their perceptions about women facing challenges pertaining to different aspects of routine life. Their thinking was captured through a 5 point scale ranging from “not at all” on one extreme to “very much” on the other. Total scores for each issue relating to women were calculated by taking the product of frequency of each source and assigned weight (-2: no/not at all; -1: I don’t think so/not really; 0: Perhaps/undecided; 1: I think so/Somewhat; 2: Yes/very much). On the basis of total scores then, ranks were assigned: 1 for the component having highest score, 2 for second highest and so on with the lowest score getting the lowest rank, 12 in this case.

Table-5 : Total Score and Ranks for Perception about Women Combating Challenges of Inequality

ISSUE	Total Score	Rank
Provision of legal rights	99	11
Educational opportunities	126	8
Economic benefits	138	4
Occupational choices	223	1
Promotions and incentives in job	134	5
Access to credit	64	12
Corporate directorships	132	7
Senior leadership positions	159	3
Property rights	181	2
Health and survival provisions	105	10
Political opportunities	121	9
Gender pay gap	133	6

For the total sample of 340 respondents, the overall score and rankings demonstrated the feelings of investors that women faced most severe challenges of inequality in occupational choices. It was with respect to occupational choices that society and its members were perceived to be headstrong as to what jobs fall exclusively in the ambit of men where women cannot penetrate owing to their physical, biological, physiological and emotional characteristics. The issue of property rights was found as next issue where women in India had to fight odds against them. Senior leadership positions and economic benefits had next highest score conveying that women experienced restricted entry to the senior leadership positions and had to forego professional and economic benefits because of gender differences prevalent in the Indian society.

Table-6 : Gender Wise Total Score and Ranks for Perception about Women Combating Challenges of Inequality

ISSUE	Male Score	Rank	Female Score	Rank
Provision of legal rights	8	11	91	8
Educational opportunities	42	5	84	9
Economic benefits	36	7	102	5
Occupational choices	92	1	131	1
Promotions and incentives in job	22	9	112	3
Access to credit	0	12	64	12
Corporate directorships	37	6	95	7
Senior leadership positions	50	3	109	4
Property rights	69	2	112	2
Health and survival provisions	22	10	83	10
Political opportunities	44	4	77	11
Gender pay gap	34	8	99	6

Access to credit and provisions of legal rights were lowest in the rung which could be attributed to the growing emphasis on women laws and protection and an effort to empower women. However, the real benefit of these empowerment initiatives in letter and spirit cannot be fathomed in the real sense as the fruits they bear are yet to be tasted. Overall scores and relative ranks of different issues highlight that efforts taken by regulators, policy holders and activists, seemed to have worked in education sector, health provisions, financial facilities, legal protection but failed to trickle down to issue of property rights, economic benefits, senior positions in work environment and occupational preferences.

Being a gender sensitive and gender related issue; the segregation and comparison of scores across gender was considered very pertinent. Responses for male and female investors were same for the first and second highest scores and related ranks. Both male and female respondents were of the belief that women face challenges primarily with respect to choice of occupation and property rights. Female investors felt that promotions and incentives in job were the next area where biases against women were common while this factor for males was 9th in importance. The perspectives are undeniably based on experiences and hence were found to differ according to the situations faced and as it is rightly said that only the bearer knows where the shoe pinches. Women, from times immemorial, combating the differential treatment have been waging losing battles to command equality for work done. The issue related to

political activities as an area of inequality have taken rank 4 for the male investors while for women it has a low rank of 11 (from a total of 12 ranks). Political activities were not regarded as an area where gender biases were prevalent while males regard it as an important area where inequalities existed. This difference in ranks for political activities emerged due to differences in choices of males and females and low number of women in active politics.

The growing emphasis in Indian lands on boosting women participation and the reverberating slogans of women equality were found in areas like grant of credit, health provisions and protection of legal rights and hence these lie low on total score for both males and females.

For the issues where women combat challenges, in spite of slight differences across gender, qualification and income of respondents, occupational choices, property rights and senior leadership positions emerge as the areas where serious challenges of inequality are perceived to be faced by women. However, access to credit and provision of legal rights were identified as areas where minimal inequalities against women were perceived to exist.

4.3. Influence of Presence of Women at Different Levels in Company on Investment Decision

Next, the respondents were requested to record their thoughts with respect to influence of women presence at different levels in corporate hierarchy from CEO level to the shop floor level. Intention was to understand if the level in the corporate hierarchy makes a difference to kind of contributions (positive, negative or no influence) women bring with their presence. Purpose was also to check that if women as team members affect decision in a certain way, does that affect differ with position they occupy in a company.

Results highlighted that contribution of women in different positions across the organizational hierarchy was not perceived to contribute negatively as supported by low frequency of responses. Overall response to the women contribution is positively concentrated, more so in the senior and higher levels where percentage of positive response was more than 50%. It was observed that at the shop floor and floor levels, a large majority of investors feel that women presence had no influence making these as gender neutral positions. Women and their finer sensibilities and capabilities were found to add to the performance and overall influence of an organization when they assumed senior, decision making and strategic positions like that of a CEO and board member.

Table-7 : Frequencies of Effect of Presence of Women at Different Levels in Company and Chi Square Values According to Gender

Level	Positively	Negatively	No influence	Chi square value (p-value) (gender)
CEO	170 (50%)	21 (6.2%)	149 (43.8%)	3.222 (0.2)
Board Member	186 (54.7%)	18 (5.3%)	136 (40%)	1.953 (0.377)
Senior Level	182 (53.5%)	16 (4.7%)	142 (41.8%)	3.849 (0.146)
Middle Manager	153 (45%)	30 (8.8%)	157 (46.2%)	3.403 (0.182)
Supervisor level	145 (42.6%)	28 (8.2%)	167 (49.1%)	1.690 (0.43)
Shop floor level	116 (34.1%)	41 (12.1%)	183 (53.8%)	1.163 (0.393)

Attempt was made to explore the differences of these responses to women contribution at different organizational levels across gender. The chi-square values together with their p-values were compiled to arrive at conclusions in the table. Results clarified that differences in responses of the investors across gender with respect to contribution of women were insignificant for all levels, right from the shop floor level to the CEO. This emphasized that males and females do not statistically differ in their perception about that women presence, and they believe that women largely contribute positively to organizational performance.

Responses lead to the interpretation that influence of women as negative is a very limiting case among the sampled investors. Contribution is believed to be positive or no effect which is found to differ not just with respect to different operating levels within the organization but also across qualification and income of the investors.

5. Conclusion

The present study is motivated by the growing chatter about the progression of women in society and corporate settings with their contributions and positions being regarded as pertinent for corporate growth and investment decisions. The investors' perceptions are attempted to be recorded to see how the investors evaluate the role of women in society, their roles vis-a-vis men and challenges women face in Indian set up. The hackneyed "glass ceiling" and its realities over the years as comprehended by common investors is intended to be recorded

and analysed to understand the true positions of women. In this context, with the help of representative and demographically distributed sample, perceptions of investors with respect to role of men and women in society and challenges of women were culled.

Various roles in the society pertaining to household, children, fund management, business decision making, political activities, social welfare etc were put together and responses of sampled investors were sought. When compared on the basis of gender, it was found that men and women respondents did differ with respect to the suitability of the two for these roles. Males and females were found to hold similar opinions on roles like kitchen and household and taking care of children. With respect to roles relating to business decision making, leading work teams and social work significant associations in responses of males and females, statistically confirmed through application of chi-square test of association, were recorded. These indicated the changing mindsets especially of women, who seemed to be defying and denying the traditional restrictions on roles which women can assume in society. Women investors and their responses advocated their ability and intention to participate equally with men in all jobs unshackling the traditional mindsets. It seemed that with changing times, women were moving beyond the clichéd role and starting to take on all responsibilities head on with a winning attitude. For the issues where women combat challenges, in spite of slight differences across gender, property rights and senior leadership positions emerge as the areas where serious challenges of inequality are perceived to be faced by women. However, access to credit and provision of legal rights were identified as areas where minimal inequalities against women were perceived to exist.

Respondents were requested to record their thoughts with respect to influence of women presence at different levels in corporate hierarchy from CEO level to the shop floor level. Intention was to understand if the level in the corporate hierarchy makes a difference to kind of contributions (positive, negative or no influence) women bring with their presence. Responses lead to the interpretation that influence of women as negative is a very limiting case among the sampled investors. Contribution is believed to be positive or no effect which is found to differ not just with respect to different operating levels within the organization but also across qualification and income of the investors.

It is concluded certain societal roles, like kitchen and household chores and taking care of children are still regarded as women's citadel while participation of women in hitherto male dominated areas is also increasing. Also, women's

presence in different rungs of the corporate ladder is looked at positively and is perceived to be progressive yet there still remains a large tract of road which is untravelled. The glass ceiling still seems to exhibit Teflon like ability in Indian settings yet deep incisions and cracks are evident. The road to equality has started to be traversed but still there are miles to go.

References

- Barney, J.B. (1991) 'Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage', *Journal of Management*, Vol. 17, pp. 99-120.
- Carter, D. A., Simkins, B. J., and Simpson, W. G. (2003) 'Corporate governance, board diversity, and firm value', *Financial Review*, Vol.38, No.1, pp. 33–53.
- Carter, D.A., Simkins, B.J., D'Souza, F. and Simpson, W.G. (2007) 'The diversity of corporate board committees and financial performance', SSRN, September 20, pp. 1-30.
- Farrell, K.A. and Hersch, P.L. (2001) 'Additions to corporate boards: does gender matter?', SSRN, November 28, pp. 1-30.
- Johnson, J.L., Daily, C.M., Ellstrand, A.E. (1996) 'Boards of directors: a review and research agenda', *Journal of Management*, Vol. 22, No.3, pp. 409–38.
- Jurkus, A.F., Park, J.C. and Woodard, L.S. (2007) 'Gender diversity and firm performance: environmentally reliant?', SSRN, pp. 1-31
- Krishnan HA, Park D. (2005) 'A few good women—on top management teams', *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 58, No.12, pp.1712–20.
- Randøy, T., Thomsen, S. and Oxelheim, L. (2006) 'A Nordic perspective on board diversity', NICE-Report, Oslo.
- Watson, W.E.; Kumar, K. and Michaelsen, L.K. (1993) 'Cultural diversity's impact on interaction process and performance: comparing homogeneous and diverse task groups', *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 36, pp. 590-602.